

Research Methodology:

Managing change in an organisation with the rapid advancement in technology.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY:

Technological advancement has supported organisations immensely and as a direct result business save time and production cost. It was identified as the biggest advantage to any organisation and also help them to gain a competitive advantage. One of the best examples of the rapid advancement of technology is Artificial Intelligence that was affected upon business and employees. This technology has a high impact on employees by reducing employment, increasing conflicts, etc. In order to overcome all issues related to changes in advancement of technology different number of useful ways was used by my chosen company here that is The chosen organisation (name withheld for NDA) This is a chosen organisation for this report, and they face some issues related to the variation in technology advancement. For this, the company followed change management and different useful ways such as select the accurate technology go via hardcore data, focus on training, involving all employees, etc. Apart from this, for collecting an accurate amount of data is important for this topic and a different number of methodologies are used such as primary and secondary source, qualitative and quantitative research, non-probability sampling, inductive approach, interpretivism philosophy, questionnaire instrument, validity and reliability of data, ethical consideration, etc. All these are an effective and important methods which help an investigator or researcher to accumulate proper information and do further research appropriately.

TITLE:

"Managing change in an organisation with the rapid advancement of technology without hurting the ethics of employees and people – a case study on The chosen organisation (name withheld for NDA)

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION:

Introduction of The Research:

A technological advancement is introduced as a generation of information and the discovery of knowledge which advances the knowingness of technology (Lucas Jr and et. al., 2013). The rate of technological advancement is rapidly increasing with time, the community is looking to develop and create easier ways to live. The internet is referred to as a massive source of information that a different number of people follow and depend on every day. Recently, there are a different number of changes in technology advancement faced by people such as 3D printing and Metal printings, Artificially manufactured embryos, Sensing city, Artificial intelligence catering to people across different walks of life, duelling neural networks, Babel-fish earbuds, Zero-carbon emitting natural gas, Perfect online privacy, Genetic fortune telling and Material's quantum leap. For this report, the given organisation is The chosen organisation (name withheld for NDA) which is a British multinational holding company located in London, United Kingdom. It was founded in 1969 and is currently chaired by Jan du Plessis and Philip Jansen. The company specialises in dealing with fixed-line telephony, mobile telephony, broadband internet, fibre-optic communication, digital television, home security and fleet management, supply chain management, telecommunication equipment, etc. Along with this, there are different important advances in business technology of The chosen organisation (name withheld for NDA) are including business management applications, email and office applications, integration applications, customer self-service, customer feedback, web conferencing, webinar applications, IP telephony, business intelligence and analytics, mobile apps, content management systems, video and audio hosting, other social network, e-commerce, virtualisation etc (Lucas and et. al., 2013).

Artificial Intelligence is referred to as an effective technology for each and every organisation. This technology can be applied to solve issues across the board. Artificial Intelligence can support businesses to detect fraud, increase sales, enhance customer experience, provide predictive analysis and automate work processes. Therefore, Artificial Intelligence is a useful system that will need to be trained and raised in more the same way as humans. One of the main problems that arise when people and employees are discussing the application of AI (Artificial Intelligence) is how to ensure that effective decisions based on technology are ethical. It is a legal and valid concern (Bose, 2013). Artificial intelligence is efficient and effective to decrease human efforts in different places. In order to perform and

do different activities in the organisation, many of them are following AI to develop machine slaves that do different activities and functions on a daily basis. Application of such technical support to get the work or activist done quicker and with appropriate outputs. Efficient and error-free worlds are the foremost purpose behind artificial intelligence.

Recently, a different number of sectors have started following AI technology to decrease efforts of human and also to get faster and efficient outputs. Apart from this, Artificial intelligence has different drawbacks like, it is a cost incurred in the repair and maintenance (Bose, 2013). An essential concern about the application of AI is about moral values and ethics. Another disadvantage of such technology as it may be able to store and record an enormous amount of information, but access and retrieval are not much effective and efficient in case of the human brain. If robots begin to replace employees in every area, it will yet lead to unemployment.

Therefore, both technology and human being are important for the success and growth of the organisation. In order to complete work and activities timely, technology is more essential whereas a human being is also required to give instruction to Robot how to work (Ertmer and Ottenbreit-Leftwich, 2013). Thus, both are necessary for their own places and support an enterprise to gain better results and outputs in future also.

Rationale of The Research:

The primary rationale behind selecting this topic is to manage the changes in organisations with the rapid advancement of technology without hurting the ethics of employees and people. It is an important topic that helps a learner and researcher to increase their knowledge and skill in a particular field of study. In order to manage changes, change management model is considered the best framework and it not harm on employees and people (Ertmer and Ottenbreit-Leftwich, 2013).

In today's world, technology is the most essential and important tool for an organisation for increasing brand awareness, loyalty, etc. But sometimes it creates different challenges and issues for the company such as leading to workers losing their jobs as more jobs become redundant with introduction of such technology (Kukulska-Hulme, 2012). There are some issues faced by organisation and employees in developing technology such as higher cost, no duplication of efforts, lesser jobs, lack of personal resourcefulness, etc. Therefore, in order to manage all these issue companies should follow a change management model, provide training to their workers, etc.

Research Aim:

“To analyse the importance of managing change in an organisation with rapid advancements of technologies without hurting ethics of employees and people”. A case study on The chosen organisation (name withheld for NDA)

Research Question:

- What is the importance of managing change in an organisation with rapid advancements of technologies without hurting the ethics of employees and people?

Research Objectives:

- To identify the concept of the rapid advancement of technology.
- To analyse the importance of change management model in managing a change of rapid advancement of technology within an organisation.
- To investigate the benefits of technological advancements for The chosen organisation (name withheld for NDA)
- To identify the ways through which The chosen organisation (name withheld for NDA) can easily overcome issue related to the rapid advancement of technology without hurting the ethics of employees and people.

Structure of the research:

This is considered the most quintessential and important part of the project which helps a researcher to identify each chapter of research. It will support an investigator to ascertain the significance of each chapter for completion of research activities effectively (Kukulka-Hulme, 2012). There is some important section of research which are identified as under:

Chapter 1: Introduction: It is considered the first and main chapter because in this entire information about the study is included. This information mainly related to the background of research, rational of study, aims, objectives, and questions (Keengwe, Schnellert, and Mills, 2012). All these are highly essential for completing research activities in an organised and a more systematic way.

Chapter 2: Literature Review: It is a type of review article and also known as scholarly paper which includes current knowledge regarding substantive findings and theoretical contribution to a specific research topic (Keengwe,

Schnellert, and Mills, 2012). It is an important section of research which help in ascertaining gaps in research and also identify conflict in the previous study. Along with this, in this part, all research objectives are addressed and analyse the opinion of authors about the topic.

Chapter 3: Methodology: It is an important and useful section of this research and help a researcher to identify different methods for collecting accurate data about the study. In this, various methods such as research philosophy, research design, qualitative and quantitative research, primary and secondary source, research issues, ethical consideration, research sampling timeline, questionnaire, and interview are included (Moolchandani and et. al., 2016). These are key to the researcher to accumulate correct data and information from participants.

Chapter 4: Data Analysis: This will be undertaken with the assistance of an analytical tool. The thematic analysis is considered as an essential analytical tool and in this case, different themes are made on each question. In order to analyse data and information from the respondents, a questionnaire is introduced best and useful instrument because it provides reliable and valid content which is related to the research topic.

Chapter 5: Conclusion and Recommendation: It is considered as the last chapter which includes the entire summary and detail information about the topic (Moolchandani and et. al., 2016). This part is based on entire research and if issues arise in this part some recommendation is provided to the company. In this recommendation, a different number of effective ways are provided which will help a researcher to overcome such issue and get better outputs for future study. It is also significant for an organisation to manage all changes which arise in the technology and achieve competitive advantages within a predetermined time period.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW:

A literature review is a comprehensive and detail summary of past research on a topic. It includes scholarly articles, books, magazines and many other relevant sources to the specific field of study. The review should describe, enumerate, summarize, objectively clarify and evaluate this previous study (Weber and Rohracher, 2012). It should provide a theoretical base for an investigation and assist the author to determine the nature of research. There are different purposes of a literature review which will help a researcher to accomplish each objective of research in a an effective and a more systematic manner. Some objectives are determined an under:

- It gives the foundation of accurate knowledge on the research topic.
- Literature review ascertains areas of prior scholarship to keep duplications and provide credit to other investigators.
- It helps in identifying inconstancies which are related to the conflict in past studies, gaps in research and open questions left from another study.
- It also assists an investigator in analysing the relationship of works in a link of its contribution to the research topic and to other work.
- This section of research helps a researcher in identifying new and unique ways to interpret the prior study.

Therefore, literature review more is more important and effective part of the researcher and support an investigator to collect in-depth and accurate data about the study. It also helps them in addressing each objective of research systematically (Muhammad, Zahari, and Sharif, 2013). All research objectives and for this opinion of different authors are determined as under:

The concept of rapid advancement of technology:

According to John Spacey, (2016), technological change is referred to as an effective process of commercialization, improvement, and invention of technology. It is a hyperbolic or exponential process whereby advance technologies develop the invention of unique technologies faster and easier resulting in accelerating change.

There is a basic type of technological change with an organisation such as productivity, efficiency, health, knowledge, entertainment, society, politics, culture, economics, industries, environment, transportation, quality of

life, etc. In today's world, modern technology is obviously developing speedily, and it is portrayed as an unfavourable influence (Weber and Rohracher, H., 2012). It can be observed that advanced technology is a transposition of the entire characteristics of life. Along with this, technology is an essential aspect of everyone lives. It is constantly enhancing its application and help an organisation to attract a large number of customers. The rapid advancement of technology has changed and modified the way the globe operates. Now, technology allows people the chances to communicate or transmit from opposite ends of the world.

On the other hand, Karehka Ramey, 2012, technology has advanced with years and it has modified the way of people about purchasing products, way of living, way of communicating a way of travelling, way of learning and so on. Advancement in technology has supported organisations, as well as business, save the cost of production and time, which has been the biggest benefits to all enterprise. With the help of technology, advancement company can easily gain competitive benefits and advantages within the given time duration. With the help of technology, an organisation can easily promote their goods and services and also retain employees for a long time by providing training to them. Training is mainly related to how to use technology and attract more customers. Advancement in technology is the biggest concept which has different advantages for an organisation such as saving time, increasing production, simplifies communication, attracting customers, etc. All these are the biggest benefits of technology advancement for an enterprise.

The importance of change management in managing a change of rapid advancement of technology within an organisation:

According to Margaret Rouse, (2018), change management is a systematic and essential approach to dealing with the transformation or transition of an organisation's processes, goals or technologies. Change management is identified as an effective process, techniques, and tools to manage the people, advancement of technology to accomplish needed business results. Change management model incorporates the business tools that can be applied to support employees or people make successful personal transitions outputting in the realization and adoption of change. Effective change management is important to each and every organisation in this fast-changing world. Main objective and purpose of change management are to increase advantages while reducing the uncertainty of failure during the implementation of change. It is also related to the communication which has been seen as an effective and two-way communication that do different functions including information sharing,

compliances, participation, and feedback. It is also essential and significant for The chosen organisation (name withheld for NDA) to manage changes in technology and achieve better results.

According to the Muhammad, Zahari and Sharif, (2013) There are different ways used by The chosen organisation (name withheld for NDA) to systematically manage all changes in technology advancement such as Identifying current loopholes, Select the right technologies, Involve their employees, Early Acceptance, Personal Incentive, Focus on Training, Pilot Operation, Expectation vs. Reality etc. All these are considered the main and essential way of change management that helps an organisation to easily manage change in technology advancement. Change management also effective and significant in managing the technology that supports an organisation to manage changes to operations. Therefore, the organisation has successfully decreased costs by ascertaining business processes and reducing actions that clients do not understand as valuable. Along with this change management is also important for a company to manage changes in technology advancement. As it gives an opportunity to the company to place decision-making power at the optimum level. Apart from this, a company can apply technology to centralise buying and logistics in order to take benefits of cost saving.

On the other hand, Change is important and necessary for each person as well as organisation. Change management is more effective and significant in managing a change of rapid advancement of technology within an organisation. Technology is the most significant part of the growth and success of an organisation. For this, the ADKAR model is more useful and have some points such as awareness, desire, knowledge, ability, and reinforcement. All these are important for an organisation to manage changes in technology and accomplish long term growth and success easily. All these points are determined as under:

- Awareness: It is mainly related to the awareness of the requirement to change technology.
- Desire: Desire to participate in and assist the change.
- Knowledge: It includes knowledge about how to change technology.
- Ability: It includes the ability to order to implement the change.
- Reinforcement: In this level, business sustains the change in an effective manner.

The benefits of technological advancements for The chosen organisation (name withheld for NDA):

As per the views of Karehka Ramey, 2012 In the current scenario every person's life is fully dependent upon the technology. It has changed them in every aspect of their life like the way they live, way of purchasing and way of communication, etc. As technology developed it impacted an individual's standard of living. Technology advancement has affected the organisation and business which resulted in the saving of time, cost, energy and smooth functioning of a company. In this context, communication is a method of exchanging or conveying the information, ideas, opinions, views, and thoughts from one person to another. For achieving or attaining anything in any aspect of life communication is needed. It is a key to success for any individual or company.

As per the viewpoint of Wheeler and Von Braun, (2013), good communication provides a positive outcome and vice versa. In the technology aspect, communication through technology plays a major role in today's telecommunication industry. In the earlier decades, only big and successful companies enjoy the benefit of technology because they can afford to it but now the advancement of internet small companies can also have the advantage in their every activity of a company. Technology has its own positive and negative effect on the company. Some of the benefits of technological advancement are as follows:

- **Increases production:** Technology is a valuable asset for every company's growth. It impacted the The chosen organisation (name withheld for NDA) 's production by saving time, cost, energy. It simplifies the activities and provided transparency of communication which makes the company perform in an easier and fastest way.
- **Exchange of Information:** Technology enables the company to exchange ideas with no hindrances from one person to another and it provides the facility of security of information. In this organisation., it allows them to convey or provide their opinion or information from country to country within a second. It reduces delay in work and can provide the data whenever required.
- **Mobility:** Technology allows companies to access their work from any part of the world i.e. any corner of the world. It impacted this organisation to be flexible in terms of expansion in various countries.
- **Increasing customer base:** Technology is important and essential for an organisation by increasing the customer base. With the help of different techniques such as social media, Instagram, Facebook, etc. company can easily introduce their products and services in the marketplace. It will support an enterprise

by improving its brand image and goodwill in the marketplace. It will also essential for The chosen organisation (name withheld for NDA) by providing information about customer's needs and wants regarding the product and services. Technology also supports an enterprise to deal with customers over the internet which will further them in saving time and cost of customers as well as the organisation also.

The ways through which The chosen organisation (name withheld for NDA) can easily overcome issue related to the rapid advancement of technology without hurting the ethics of employees and people:

As per the views of Jabil, 2017, In this modern business era, there is rapid change arises in the technologies, thus the major concern area of each small, as well as large business enterprises, is to adopt changes in their technologies in respect to maintaining its competitive position. Organisations are undergoing a digital transformation and have likely enjoyed the enhanced market share and customer engagement, higher employee morale or developed customers revenue. The chosen organisation (name withheld for NDA) is the famous telecommunications provider company which is focused towards developing its operations by making advancement in their technologies or operations. The company has faced issues related with the rapid changes arises in the technology, thus the company has applied different ways to overcome with the issue of rapid changes in the technology without hurting employees as well as human's ethics. The potential ways are associated as below:

Handling Employee Pushback During Digital Transformation: Experiencing a digital transformation is the prototype of discomfort, so it may make employees feel threatened or dissatisfied. It is essential to consider that sometimes changes are necessary to keep up with the times because sometimes not changing is much riskier. The digital transformation is essential for this organisation as to providing an appropriate environment and facilities to their employees.

Develop a Company-Wide Digital Transformation Strategy: This organisation is operating at a wide scale and the major concern of the firm is to attaining high growth and success through developing its business operations by making appropriate changes in their technologies (Blau, Brummund and Liu, 2013). The company or its management are concern towards creating an effective wide digital transformation strategy with respect to make changes without hurting employees or people.

Finding the Expertise to Lead Digitization Initiatives: The Organisation is operating at a wide scale and deals in multiple telecommunication services and products (Oesch,2013). Advancement in technologies are crucial for organisations, thus the management of the organisation hire experts within their workplace in respect to making changes or transformation with the appropriate guidance of experts.

Accurate training and development: It is as an effective way through which The chosen organisation (name withheld for NDA) can easily overcome issue related to the rapid advancement on technology without hurting ethics of employees and people (Gill and et. al., 2014). For this, the company provides accurate training to their employees who have a lack of knowledge about technology. Thus, accurate training helps employees to use technology and gain better advantages within the given time duration.

Academic theory: Lewin's Change Management Model is considered the best academic theory which will help an organisation to retain employees by providing all information about the advancement in technology. This framework includes three stages which are determined as under:

Unfreeze: This first stage of change model involves preparing the enterprise to accept that change is essential, which includes breaking down the present status quo before they can develop up a new way of operating. In this stage, The chosen organisation (name withheld for NDA) introduces entire detail about the technology to their employees which will help workers by increasing its skills without hurting them.

Change: After the uncertainty developed in the unfreeze stage, the change or variation stage is where employees begin to resolve their issues and look for innovative ways to do things. Employees of The chosen organisation (name withheld for NDA) start to believe as well as act in ways that assist the new direction.

Refreeze: It is the last stage in this change are taking shape and employees have embraced the innovative ways of working, the The chosen organisation (name withheld for NDA) is ready to refreeze. In this phase, the company solves all issues of employees about the technology by providing training.

Conceptual framework:

(Source: Conceptual Framework of advancement in Technology, 2019)

From the above-mentioned chart, it has been interpreted advancement in technology which is beneficial for an organisation to retain employees long time and attain better outputs within a given time duration. In this chart, there are basically two variables such as dependent and independent (Kulo and Bodzin, 2013). Employee capability, knowledge sharing, working culture, working culture, research, and development capability, and communication capability mainly depends on an absorptive transfer performance. Managing change in The chosen organisation (name withheld for NDA) with the rapid advancement of technology without hurting the ethics of employees and people, this framework highly helps them to retain employees for a long time.

CHAPTER 3: METHODOLOGY:

A research methodology is an important part of a dissertation which is used by a researcher to gather data and information for the motive of making business decisions in an accurate manner. The methodology may include interviews, publication research, survey and many other relevant techniques (Wheeler and Von Braun, 2013). It could also include both historical as well as present information which is related to the topic. The purpose of the research is to find answers to questions via the utilisation of scientific and effective procedures. Along with this, the main aim of the methodology is to discover the truth which is invisible, and which has not been disclosed as yet. There is some important purpose of research methodology in regard to a topic are determined as under:

- The main purpose of the research methodology is to test a hypothesis or theory of a causal relationship between variables.
- To collect an accurate and relevant amount of data from the respondents which is mainly related to the research or topic.

Therefore, this section includes different methods and approaches which will help a researcher to accumulate proper data about the study (Blau, Brummund. and Liu, 2013). Some important and useful method according to the topic is determined as under:

Research Philosophy:

Research philosophy is referred to as a large topic and it mainly deals with the nature, sources, and development of knowledge or skill by the investigator. In addition, it can be defined that the essential ways by which investigator gather, analyse data or information related to the study. Research philosophy is divided into three parts such as positivism, interpretivism, and pragmatism. All these are essential for the researcher to collect appropriate information about the topic and gain better results for future study. The method of research philosophy applied in this study is pragmatism because it is matched with all other remaining philosophy and can be used in an easy manner. Positivism and interpretivism philosophy of research is not suitable because it did not give and fit as per the research requirements (Gill and et. al., 2014). As such types of methods emphasised on following the frameworks and theories in order to ascertain solutions for the problems.

Justification: Pragmatism philosophy will be applied in the project which will support in evaluating information effectively and accurately. As it will also assist in arriving appropriate and accurate conclusion for the research (Lee, Trimi and Kim, 2013). On the other side, there is interpretivism and positivism philosophy which be not appropriate and suitable for executing research activities in a systematic manner. Thus, pragmatism philosophy is useful for organisation or researcher to collect data about Managing change in an enterprise with the rapid advancement of technology without paining the ethics of workers and people.

Research Design:

The entire research depends on a research design which is executed by an investigator for ascertaining impact in research. There is mainly three types of design namely exploratory, descriptive and experimental. According to the research or topic, the descriptive design is used because it helps a researcher to derive a valid and effective conclusion for a research. In the case of experimental design, it is applied to establish an effective relationship between the effect and cause of a situation (Oesch, 2013). Under exploratory design, thoughts and ideas of researchers are key as it primarily relies on their personal inclination regarding a specific topic. At last, in the case of descriptive design, an investigator is exclusively interested in explaining the case or situation under its research.

Justification: According to the research topic, the descriptive design is used because it is a theory based and help an investigator to collect, presents and analyse gathered information. Thus, it is more useful and significant design and helps a researcher to collect valid information or data related to the topic (Whitehead, Jensen and Boschee, 2013).

Research Methods:

There are a different number of methods in research used by an investigator to collect accurate and reliable information related to the study. Some important and useful research methods are explained as under:

- **Research Choice:** It defines an effective way in which information is followed by an investigation for completing research activities. The method applied in the field of study choice are quantitative and qualitative and the selection in between them relays on the nature and kind of research (Kulo and Bodzin, 2013).

Justification: According to the topic, the qualitative research method is followed in order to accumulate data related to the research (Maxwell, 2012). On the other hand, there is a quantitative method, it is applied in case when figures and calculation are required. Thus, for this topic, there is no requirement of facts and numbers so qualitative research is followed.

- **Primary and secondary source:** According to the research topic, there are basically two types of sources such as primary and secondary. In the case of primary research, a questionnaire is used to collect reliable and valid data related to the topic (Lee, Trimi and Kim, 2013). On the other side, under a secondary researcher, the researcher needs a different number of books, journals, publication research, magazines, etc. to accumulate in-depth data about the study. Therefore, primary source, help an organisation or researcher to identify the impact of changes in technology advancement for employees or people.
- **Research Approach:** It can be said as the procedures and plans set up to organise the research activity in a systematic manner (Kesharwani and Singh Bisht, 2012). There are mainly two types of research approaches such as deductive and inductive.

Justification: According to the research topic, the deductive research approach is applied because it will support in accomplishing objectives and goal of research. In this, the use of the questionnaire instrument will be completed in order to know the problem and address the issue (Whitehead, Jensen and Boschee, 2013). On the other hand, in the case of the inductive approach, it is not suitable and useful for the topic because it is based on existing theory.

- **Research sampling:** It is identified as an effective method and in which a different number of persons, items or objects are taken from an entire population. There are basically two types of research sampling which name are probability and non-probability (Kelly, Lesh and Baek, 2014). Along with this, probability sampling is an effective technique and in which subjects of the entire population get the same changes to be chosen as a representative sample. Under, non-probability, it is also considered as a type of sampling method and in which population does not get equal opportunity.

Justification: Apart from this, according to the research topic, convenience sampling as a type of non-probability method is used, because it does not require more and time as well as also provide better results for research (Kim, Im and Slater, 2013).

- **Research instrument:** There are different types of research instrument such as questionnaire, interview, survey, observation, etc. All these are essential but according to the research topic, questionnaire instrument as a part of primary research is used (Maxwell, 2012). As it helps an investigator by providing reliable and valid information related to the influence of changes in technology. Apart from this, interview, observation, and survey are also useful, but it requires more time of researcher, so it is not used in this research.
- **Research validity and reliability:** It is also an essential section of research methodology and in which an investigator has to into consideration. It is important and assists the investigator in getting known regarding the validity and reliability of study on which they are doing. So, in the study for making the information valid and reliable for a long duration, the application of the questionnaire is completed (Kesharwani and Singh Bisht, 2012). It is significant and useful for the researcher to accumulate reliable and valid data about the changes in technology advancement and its impact on business and employees.
- **Time Horizon:** This is also considered an essential part of research methodology which helps a researcher to find out starting and ending time of research completion. For this, a Gantt chart is introduced effective technique and graphical presentation which help in identifying time duration about the research (Przybylski, and Weinstein, 2013).

TASKS	RESPONSIBLE	START	END	DAYS	STATUS
Research Prposal	Romit Ray	04-Nov-18	10-Jan-19	67	Complete
Presentation of Research proposal	Romit Ray	20-Dec-18	16-Jan-19	27	Complete
Introduction	Romit Ray	01-Apr-19	16-May-19	45	Not started
Literature relew	Romit Ray	05-Dec-18	30-Aug-19	268	In Progress
Research Design	Romit Ray	07-Jul-19	05-Sep-19	60	Not started
Methods Chapter	Romit Ray	07-Jul-19	05-Oct-19	90	Not started
Fieldwork	Romit Ray	01-Apr-19	28-Sep-19	180	Not started
Data Analysis	Romit Ray	29-Sep-19	28-Nov-19	60	Not started
Findings Chapter	Romit Ray	01-Dec-19	31-Dec-19	30	Not started
Final Draft	Romit Ray	01-Jan-20	31-Mar-20	90	Not started
Viva Preparation	Romit Ray	01-Apr-20	16-Apr-20	15	Not started
Thesis	Romit Ray	01-Aug-19	30-Nov-20	487	Not started

Gantt chart for project phases

Access to Issues and Ethical Consideration:

The main ethical problem for this research is the respondent's right or power to anonymity and too few extent denials of advantages for the control team in forms of decreased work time. In order to justify these problems, workers identify will remain absence and an anonymous record will only be attended by the workers' respective demographic profile. In addition, research ethics means that an investigator must be completed in an accurate manner and entire data given in the research are real and accurate (Kelly, Lesh and Baek, 2014). Principles of research ethics were utilised such as confidentiality, anonymity and informed consent. Along with this, the details given in the study are not recorded and collected from an unknown source. In other words, the research activity is also completed to applied it for a lawful motive, not for any illegal one. At last, outputs must be communicated with only those people who has their involvement in the field of study.

Therefore, time is considered the main issue for this research because, in order to collect an accurate amount of data about how to manage changes in an organisation with the fast advancement of technology without paining ethics of employees and people, the researcher needs sufficient time (Kim, Im and Slater, 2013). As a whole, for completing research activities systematically and effectively, proper time is required.

CHAPTER 4: CONCLUSION:

From the above-mentioned information, it has been concluded that the advancement of technology is essential for the growth and success of the company. It also helps an organisation to increase the customer base and improve their brand image at the market. There are a different number of methods used to collect accurate information about the study such as primary and secondary source, qualitative and quantitative research, sampling method, questionnaire, research philosophies, design, and approaches. All these are the most effective method which will help an investigator or organisation to get better results in a future study. For this, different ways are followed by the company to effectively manage changes in technology advancement without hurting employees and many other people. Along with this, the company follows change management which will support them in handling changes in technology as well as it also helps in retaining employees for a long time. Thus, it is essential for future growth and development of the company within a predetermined time period. Along with this, various number of essential ways are also used by the company to overcome challenges related to the rapid advancement of technology without hurting the ethics of employees and people. For this company should identify current loopholes, select the right and accurate technology, involve them all workers, etc. Thus, all these are effective and beneficial for the success and growth of the organisation in a given time period.

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